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Exploring the potential of local stakeholders' involvement in crisis management. The living lab approach in a case study from amsterdam

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the outcome of research into the potential of local stakeholders' involvement in crisis management in two Amsterdam neighborhoods. It addresses the recognized challenge of enabling and improving collaboration between established formal response organizations and local actors engaged in extending and emergent organizational behavior during crises. To further explore the potential of local actors in responding to a crisis, the authors adopted the living lab approach to bring together actors from established response organizations, the municipality and local stakeholders. The so-called Amsterdam Crisis Resilience Living Lab, set up in the Zuidas and Indische Buurt neighborhoods, enabled the co-creation of knowledge produced by both formal organizations and local stakeholders in close collaboration with researchers from the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam and the Institute for Societal Resilience. The results and lessons learned show potential of collaboration between formal, traditional response organizations and local stakeholders in crisis response. Strengthening the links between them can ultimately lead to a more inclusive and resilient crisis management approach. In addition the article shows the added value of the living lab approach in bringing together multiple responding stakeholders from different backgrounds.

1. Introduction

While the world has always known disruptions, today's globalization, rapid urbanizations, and climate change create a sense of urgency. Incidents and disasters are having broader, longer-lasting effects, which means that societies have to continuously adapt and respond to the challenges those effects create [1]. Despite the global character of current crises, they hit locally, often with severe consequences for local communities. Current crises are characterized by multiple causes, ambiguous effects, and various means of resolu-

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tion that require active involvement of all parties in the response, including established and institutionalized response organizations and other stakeholders such as community organizations, citizens groups, and private businesses [2,3].

A crisis or a disaster (the labels are often used interchangeably) occurs when a social system, such as a community, organization, policy sector, or country, experiences an urgent threat to its basic structures or fundamental values, one that involves uncertainties and appears to require a profound and far-reaching response [1,4]. The crisis management literature distinguishes between a trigger event (e.g., flooding, power outage, heat wave) and the resulting social, community, or organizational crisis. A trigger event can result in a crisis if a society, community, or organization is vulnerable “in terms of their capacity to anticipate, cope with, resist and recover from the impact of a natural hazard. [Vulnerability] involves a combination of factors that determine the degree to which someone's life and livelihood is put at risk by a discrete and identifiable event in nature or society” ([5], p. 28).

Thus, a crisis occurs when the demands of a trigger event exceed the society's, community's, or organization's ability to respond, resulting in a threat to its continuation. Crisis management then is seen as the “process of how we prepare for, respond to and learn from the effects of a wide range of major failures that impact upon groups of people, from organizations to local, national and international communities” ([6], p. 813). For first responders and crisis managers, a crisis often refers to a state of emergency, meaning that a society, community, or organization cannot cope with the consequences of the trigger event and external help is needed.

Though traditional crisis response parties' skillful following of plans and procedures, known as the “command and control method”, has long predominated crisis management, increasing attention is being given to crisis management approaches that make room for local actors who, in addition to and ideally in collaboration with professional emergency services, contribute to the crisis management process [7–9]. Their understanding of the local situation and their embeddedness in local networks are key assets to creating more inclusive crisis responses. Various studies in crisis management have shown that a wide variety of local stakeholders including community organizations, citizens networks, and spontaneous volunteers emerge to provide aid during disasters and crises [10–14].

However, *how* to align their actions with the formal response structures is still a burning question that can be best answered *in collaboration with* the local actors. To further explore the potential of local stakeholders – including citizens communities, spontaneous volunteers, shop/business owners - in responding to a crisis, we adopted the living lab approach to bring together actors from the established response organizations, the municipality, and local stakeholders. Schliwa and McCormick ([15], p. 174) see a living lab as “both a physical location and a joint approach, in which different parties experiment, co-create and test in a lifelike environment, delimited by geographical and institutional boundaries”. Living labs have been developed and implemented in innovative studies in order to include citizens' lifeworlds and increase citizens' influence in a municipality and its development [16]. Past living labs have had various aims: for example, to stimulate user-driven innovation for sustainability [17]. More recently, the approach has gained the attention of researchers and policy makers due to its proven potential in developing, implementing, and monitoring interventions to solve urban challenges in innovative ways.

Until now, the living lab approach has been less well known in disaster and crisis studies and management. However, it has great potential for bringing together various actors to find local solutions in all phases of the disaster management cycle. This article therefore introduces the living lab approach as a form of action research to the field of crisis management as an instrument to improve the alignment between formal response organizations and local stakeholders. The research for the article was guided by the following questions: How can the actions by formal crisis response organizations and local stakeholders be better aligned and how can the living lab approach facilitate the alignment?

This article presents research on the potential of local stakeholders during crises in Amsterdam. The research was carried out by members of the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam and the Institute for Societal Resilience in collaboration with the Municipality of Amsterdam and the Safety Region Amsterdam-Amstelland, the safety region³ in which the municipality is embedded. It builds on previous studies of citizens' involvement in neighborhood development and community building [18] and on studies of local initiatives by spontaneous volunteers involved in the reception of refugees and status holders in Amsterdam during the so-called refugee crisis in 2015 [19,20]. In recent years, the municipality and the safety region have invested in improving the quality of collaborations between the different professional response organizations, including the fire brigade, police, and medical teams [21]. On the basis of experience gained in past crises, and during the refugee crisis in particular, they have also started to realize that the knowledge and expertise of various local stakeholders is crucial in crisis management.

In the remainder of this article, we first elaborate on crisis management and resilience. Next, we present how we designed and set up the living lab in Amsterdam. We describe how various crisis cases and scenarios were selected and discussed in the living lab and use a process approach to explain the various stages of the living lab step by step, highlighting the lessons learned for the living lab methodology and for the actual practice of crisis management. Finally, we present the main lessons learned of the living lab application in Amsterdam in the discussion and end with a brief conclusion.

2. A crisis resilience perspective: bringing various stakeholders together

From the resilience perspective, traditional crisis response partners – rather than trying to control societal initiatives – are challenged to collaborate with local initiatives [22,23]. Such a resilience view sees disruptive events as enablers to change and to new initiatives that may have been previously seen as impossible or unfeasible [6,10,13,24]. In this article, we build on the notion of societal resilience by zooming in on the adaptive capacity of crisis management in Amsterdam. While resilience has long been seen as focus-

³ Safety Regions in the Netherlands (in Dutch: Veiligheidsregio) is a public body whose task it is to facilitate regional cooperation in dealing with crises, disasters and disruptions of public order. The Safety Region forms the basis for multidisciplinary (inter)action i.e. between the police, fire service and medical emergency teams.

ing on the “bouncing back” of systems under pressure [25], resilience scholars have begun to consider complex social-technical systems and the notions of adaptation and transformation of social systems [26]. In the 1970s, the term became increasingly used in resource management, engineering and ecology. The ecologist Holling [27,28] introduced resilience as a lens to study how natural systems could reach stability after an unforeseen and severe shock. Since, the concept has been used in a variety of disciplines to understand processes of adaptation and transformation. In the social sciences it became an approach to exploring the responses of individuals, organizations and communities when confronted with severe challenges [29]. In this view, resilience is seen as “the capacity of a social system to proactively adapt to and recover from disturbances that are perceived within the system to fall outside the range of normal and expected disturbances” ([30], p. 9). It addresses the ability of local actors to anticipate, prepare for, reduce the impact of, cope with, and recover from the effects of shocks and stresses [31,32]. With the focus on reducing the impact of a disaster by building on the peoples’ capacities the concept of resilience got a positive connotation. At the same time, resilience is a heavily contested concept because it became part of neo-liberal narratives and policies aiming at decreasing state involvement by counting the self-reliance of society without providing the proper conditions and as such a way to restructure social services [33–35]. In the context of a crisis, this means that authorities are encouraging and sometimes mandating local stakeholders to become self-reliant without providing them the proper support and resources [36,37].

While we recognize the need to critically approach neo-liberal bias in the way the term resilience has been used by policy makers and politicians, in this article we use resilience as a lens to recognize and do justice to the actions of local stakeholders aiming at strengthening the adaptive capacity of the crisis response system in Amsterdam. By adopting the resilience lens we would like to emphasize the potential of local stakeholders’ capacities in response to crises [30,38]. In particular we will focus on issues of collaboration and coordination because, while based on the studies on previous crisis situation we can foresee that local stakeholders will become active, it is hard to predict exactly who those stakeholders are or will be, how they are organized and what kind of activities they will employ. Before, crisis response actions of local stakeholders have been studied from the perspective of *convergence*. In those studies the question how the stakeholders’ actions can be moving toward union or uniformity was central [39].

Convergence is indeed a challenge as many *different types of organized behavior* appear at the disaster site. For example, after the 2001 attacks on the Twin Towers in New York City, the collapse of the towers left much of Manhattan in smoke and rubble; public transportation stopped running and bridges and tunnels closed. Many New Yorkers had no way to evacuate the island. However, a network of ferries, tugs, dinner boats, and fishing boats emerged spontaneously to take people safely to the mainland. Ultimately, by converting their skills into a coordinated effort, New York Harbor sailors and employees managed to evacuate an estimated 300,000 to 500,000 stranded people trapped on the shore of Lower Manhattan in about 10 h [40]. The US Coast Guard, rather than trying to take control or manage an evacuation that was both unforeseen and far beyond what anyone could have imagined, embraced the spontaneous actions by seeking collaboration and ways to work together. Subsequently, the Coast Guard even put out a radio call for “all available boats”. This example shows that complex and diverse networks in which various local stakeholders reside and in which collaborative efforts take place can reduce the effects of a crisis [41,42].

To unravel the complexity of organized behavior, Dynes and his colleagues defined the tasks that groups perform at disaster sites and their corresponding organizational structure [43,44] (see Table 1).

In this typology, Type 1 organized behavior is performed by established organizations, such as the police and the fire brigade, that carry out their regular tasks based on protocols and standard operating procedures. Type 2 behavior involves expanding organizations such as the Red Cross. Such organizations work in the field of crisis management. They exist before the crisis occurs but are able to expand in response to the crisis, for example, by mobilizing trained volunteers. In Type 3 behavior, extending organizations perform tasks outside of their traditional role. For example, in response to Hurricane Katrina in the southern United States, Walmart, a multinational retail corporation that operates a chain of supermarkets, discount department stores, and grocery stores from the United States, provided food and logistical support to the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) and other response organizations [45,46]. Finally, Type 4 behavior includes emergent groups with unstable memberships, such as spontaneous volunteers and citizens groups, performing non-regular tasks [47].

Since the focus of this paper is to understand the alignment between traditional and local stakeholders, we will zoom in on Types 3 and 4 of organized behavior: extending and emergent organized behavior. Previous research has shown that improving collaboration between formal, traditional and informal, non-traditional partners requires a careful understanding of the relationships between them [13,48]. To enable smooth(er) collaboration, formal crisis response organizations need to familiarize themselves with how their non-traditional crisis response partners think, operate, and work because they have an important role to play when it comes to coordination. They need to invest in understanding who these partners are, how they are organized, and how they become active at times of crisis. Similarly, for non-traditional stakeholders, gaining insights into how formal crisis response organizations work can enable their initiatives to become more effective and efficient.

However, the likelihood that cooperation will happen between extending and emergent groups and formal response organizations cannot be assumed, because the standard operating procedures and protocols of traditional crisis response parties are often inward looking and inflexible [10]. In addition, because extending and emergent forms of organized behavior involve non-registered actors’

Table 1
Types of organized behavior at disaster sites (based on Dynes and Aguirre [35]).

	Regular tasks	Non-regular tasks
Old structures	Type 1. Established	Type 3. Extending
New structures	Type 2. Expanding	Type 4. Emergent

actions undirected by formal emergency response, their legitimization does not come from a formalized and centralized authority; their effectiveness is therefore questioned by formal authorities [49,50]. Their actions are seen as peripheral and unpredictable, and more often than not, they are treated as a liability [48,51]. Relationships between these groups are part of the complex power dynamics that include the dominance of the main institutional crisis management design (for example command and control systems), the compliance to the logic of that design, and the struggle to overcome the barriers between that design and the interests and values of other designs, such as emergent and spontaneous actions [52]. Yet, there is much to be gained from understanding how formal crisis management organizations may work together with local stakeholders. If collaboration between them can be improved, it may potentially lead to more resilient crisis management [14,16,22]. This is where the living lab approach comes in.

3. The living lab approach

When designed properly, living labs can create an environment for open-innovation intermediaries [53], where different stakeholders participate in co-creative social settings to work on and strengthen emerging solutions that exist at the local level. Recently, urban living labs gained popularity as they are embedded in and part of a new collaborative approach aimed at improving governance in cities at the neighborhood level [54]. Due to the relative novelty of the term, a widely supported academic definition does not yet exist [55,56]. Nevertheless, three recurring characteristics can be distinguished in the literature.

First, in a living lab approach, *co-creation* is central [26]. Living labs are presented as platforms where all relevant parties come together to jointly create research questions and produce knowledge [57]. Knowledge co-creation can be defined as “a form of knowledge development in which researchers from different scientific fields collaborate with societal stakeholders” ([58], p.12). In addition, knowledge co-creation is “focused on jointly shaping new solutions for the city” ([58], p.12).

Second, a living lab takes an experimental, *learning approach* in a pre-given environment [54,57,59]. This means that research is not carried out solely by the knowledge institution; instead the institution and societal stakeholders work together to take a practical look at what could work in a particular context (experimental) and what the next steps in decision making should be depending on the local solution (learning by doing). For example, the living lab discussed in this article used “ideal typical” historical cases (power outage, house fire, terrorist attack) and an actual ongoing crisis situation (i.e., the COVID-19 outbreak) to focus on resilient crisis management and communication.

Third, a living lab has to include a *diversity of stakeholders* [57]. Since living labs are organized in a specific local context, both local communities and governmental bodies operating in that environment have to be involved to make sure the outcomes will be followed up. The involvement of formal crisis organizations - in the case of this article - offers opportunities for exploring a new relationship between the roles of disaster relief organizations and citizens' initiatives (i.e., the traditional and non-traditional crisis response partners).

While there is no blueprint to designing and setting up living labs as an intervention, an important characteristic is that the implementation typically takes place in different phases (following Majoor et al. [54]): the exploration, the start phase, the development and implementation phase, and the evaluation and monitoring phase. In the following, we use these phases to show how a living lab called the *Amsterdam Crisis Resilience Living Lab* was set up in Amsterdam with the aim of understanding how established first response organizations and the local stakeholders, including citizen groups, spontaneous volunteers and shop/business owners, each work and how they can improve collaboration and enable coordination.

4. The co-creation method

The *Amsterdam Crisis Resilience Living Lab* (in short Amsterdam Living Lab) was built on promising emergent crisis response structures at the local level. We used it as a “real-life setting” to co-create knowledge about the sustainability of the emerging initiatives [60,61]. The *co-creation* of knowledge was central from the very start: through various co-creation sessions, representatives from the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam and the Institute for Societal Resilience, the Municipality of Amsterdam, the Safety Region Amsterdam-Amstelland, the private sector, and members of citizens groups defined the problem to be investigated. They also established a joint framework in which the building blocks of this new resilient crisis approach would be explored, analyzed, and elaborated. These building blocks subsequently provided a concrete form to the Amsterdam Living Lab. The following starting questions emerged:

- What are the characteristics of the resilient crisis approach from the perspectives of traditional and non-traditional stakeholders/crisis response partners (sensemaking)?
- What does this new approach mean for (the design of) formal crisis management organizations (such as their standard operating procedures) and the municipality (their policies and crisis communication)?

These questions helped to guide the research that was jointly conducted in the Amsterdam Living Lab. That research examined past crisis situation cases (or “scenarios”) and the current COVID-19 crisis with the aim of creating and implementing a resilient crisis management approach. Beginning in mid-2019, several exploratory discussions were held with potential interested parties. These contacts came from existing networks in the municipality, the safety region, and the knowledge institute. For example, discussions were held with crisis and communication advisors within the municipality, with neighborhood associations and knowledge brokers (civil servants in particular), and with researchers who had already worked with living labs in various settings. Thus, a broad *diversity* of parties were consulted to ensure that the design and development of the Amsterdam Living Lab was supported by a wide range of stakeholders.

The results of this initial phase were used as input for the Amsterdam Living Lab's first meeting, which took place on June 24, 2019. Participants were selected through a careful stakeholder analysis. More than 40 relevant companies and organizations were in-

vited to participate, including academics, policy makers, and private and public organizations. The meeting looked at jointly exploring the focus of the project and creating support within the participating stakeholders. We organized several dialogue tables to discuss questions using concrete crisis scenarios such as power outage, heat wave, terrorist attack, or pandemic. Participants at each table discussed the following questions: If a crisis were to occur in your neighborhood:

- What is the expected dynamic: Who would take action? Who (in your opinion) is responsible for what?
- What do the relevant stakeholders know about each other? What role do they play in crisis management and communication?

On the basis of this input, we organized various meetings as part of the development and implementation phase in 2019–2020. During the Amsterdam Living Lab's meetings and activities, participants organized focus group meetings to discuss solutions at the local level [62]. We also held informal interviews with the participants to understand how they made sense of the activities. We used the experience of Petra Ardai, theater producer and screenwriter and co-author of this article, to help participants to think and act effectively outside of their comfort zones. Another member, Stella de Kort, an independent illustrator and also a co-author of this article made several pictures of crises scenarios to help stimulate participants' imaginations as they discussed the crises and citizens' actions. The illustrations enabled participants to position themselves as realistically as possible in situations in which a lot could go wrong but opportunities to help also existed.

5. Working with concrete scenarios at the neighborhood level

During the dialogue table discussions, the Amsterdam neighborhoods Zuidas and Indische Buurt were mentioned as the two most promising research locations. The Zuidas is a financial district on the south side of Amsterdam. It is dominated by high-rise buildings, large infrastructure, and extensively used space. The Zuidas brings together working and living functions of the city; it is a place of urban transformation, offering office space and housing alongside hotels and service facilities. The Indische Buurt, a neighborhood in the eastern part of Amsterdam, reflects the cultural diversity in Amsterdam. About 55% of its residents have a non-western migrant background, with mostly Moroccan, Turkish, and Surinamese origins. For example, housing corporations have been revitalizing the neighborhood, partly by transforming social housing into owner-occupied housing. Gentrification has become a main driver of social change here [15,63,64]. These two neighborhoods have completely different dynamics and - although comparative, raising questions about how resilient each neighborhood might be during a crisis and whether the differences in population and social dynamics would play a role.

5.1. Introducing the living lab in the Amsterdam Zuidas neighborhood

To set up the Amsterdam Living Lab in the Zuidas, we contacted Hello Zuidas, an organization that aims to create an optimally functioning and attractive neighborhood for all people and organizations located there. It plays a key role in the neighborhood and organizes a (private) safety platform a few times a year, where companies and organizations working in the Zuidas can learn from each other. According to Hello Zuidas's website, "The Zuidas Safety Platform is an alliance of local businesses, law enforcement, municipal authorities and the Safety Region Amsterdam-Amstelland. Most Hello Zuidas members delegate a facility manager or head of security to represent them within the platform. Its aim is to exchange knowledge and experience on how to respond to incidents and emergencies".⁴

Together with Hello Zuidas, we organized two scenario sessions at the World Trade Center's (WTC) high-rise building in the neighborhood, see [picture 1](#). The sessions focused on safety consequences in the area in relation to energy transition. Participants discussed a scenario based on recent news reports about a disruption in the electricity supply and on National Safety Strategy policy documents regarding the vulnerability of "vital infrastructures".⁵ The scenario was also informed by an actual crisis situation: a large-scale power outage that occurred on March 27, 2015 in North Holland [65]. This power outage also affected the WTC building in which the sessions were being held. During the sessions, the building's property manager, who was on duty during the 2015 power outage, explained how the evacuation of the WTC took place. The crisis situation taught him that both citizens and governments needed to be more aware of the limitations of telecommunications during a power outage, and it made clear the importance of partnerships in facilitating evacuations during an outage.

Given this input, traditional and non-traditional crisis response partners discussed what might happen if another power outage were to occur in the Zuidas. Participants included representatives from the Municipality of Amsterdam, the Safety Region Amsterdam-Amstelland, citizens from a local residents' association, the police, the fire brigade, and five private organizations including banks and consultancy firms. The central question during these sessions focused on how the firms and the citizens in the neighborhood would deal with uncertainties during a power outage. What kind of dynamics would emerge? Would networks of citizens and/or companies take action, and if so, what actions would they take? What would be expected of each other?

See [Picture 1](#) in the Appendix.

[Picture 1](#). Scenario session in the Amsterdam Zuidas neighborhood.

The main challenge all the participating stakeholders could foresee is that while information and communication flows are often well organized within a single organization in Zuidas, there is less knowledge about how the organization will share information with others and if/how it will reach out to formal and informal response organizations and networks. The scenario revealed that organizations are highly dependent on mobile telephones and social media for crisis communication. Participants did not know how crisis

⁴ <https://www.helloZuidAs.com/nieuws/ZuidAs-safety-platform-ZuidAs-can-t-guard-against-emergency-5f6b1c1c21183c7e134df5f8>.

⁵ <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/rapporten/2019/06/07/tk-bijlage-nationale-strategie-2019>.

communication would be handled without electricity. While standalone facilities for supplying energy such as emergency aggregates would still work, the organizations would eventually run into problems if the power outage continued for too long.

The discussion also revealed that individual organizations would inform mainly their own people via, for example, facility services, company emergency response teams (required by the government), or management or owners' associations, according to their own mandates, procedures, and routines. Though they would *extend* their actions in order to respond to the crisis, their focus would be more on business continuity and less on the neighborhood and other organizations and networks. This raised the following questions: How will organizations share information about what is going on? With whom? And above all, who will communicate with the public about what is happening and on whose behalf?

To answer this challenge, Hello Zuidas recently developed an emergency app for companies located in and around the Zuidas area. In the event of a significant emergency, the app will send messages to keep everyone informed, assuming that such communication still works during a power failure. It also appeared that more attention could be given to strengthening cooperation between different emergency response departments, improving connections between organizations in the neighborhood, and gaining more insight into the role of emergency services and the municipality. For example, at one point, the police indicated that they increasingly rely on citizens and companies to manage themselves in certain situations, such as if the entire WTC building has been evacuated and all the people are standing outside. While this was seen as an opportunity for the emergency responders to make their evacuation practices more effective, it also revealed that the current organizational protocols and standard operating procedures did not take this expectation into account.

5.2. Introducing the living lab in the Indische Buurt neighborhood

The Amsterdam Living Lab in the Indische Buurt was set up in close collaboration with an active local neighborhood community. Because the project team had existing connections with the members of De Meevaart,⁶ a neighborhood center in the Indische Buurt, contacting them about the living lab was relatively easy. In the run-up to the scenario session, two pilot sessions were held: one with traditional crisis response parties, including the fire brigade and the police, and one with non-traditional crisis response parties. This was done to informally introduce the participants, while in their own safe environments, to the Amsterdam Living Lab, its importance, and how the project team would work. The aim of the pilot sessions was to make the participants co-researchers in the project by involving them in co-creation sessions.

The main issue emerging from the discussions was that citizens are not always seen or appreciated in the actions taken by the formal response organizations, although the conversations also showed that this attitude is changing. For example, the police recently invested in building links between themselves and citizen networks in the Indische Buurt in order to create good relationships with key organizations and key persons in the neighborhood. Because the pilot sessions provided a place for all those present to share their concerns, ideas, and questions, they created the necessary trust to jointly design the scenarios.

On March 5, 2020, we organized a larger scenario session at De Meevaart to investigate the role of citizens as non-traditional partners and to explore the challenges traditional crisis response partners face when working with them. About 20 participants were present at the meeting: active local residents and police department employees as well as representatives from the Municipality of Amsterdam, the Safety Region Amsterdam-Amstelland, the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam and the Institute for Societal Resilience. This meeting served two purposes: (a) to exchange knowledge about citizen participation during (fictional) crisis scenarios and (b) to create awareness about any added value from cooperation between traditional and non-traditional, *emergent* crisis response parties during a crisis.

During the sessions, two scenarios were discussed in subgroups. The group members had diverse backgrounds and consisted of traditional crisis response parties and citizens. The process of negotiation during the fictitious crisis situation, the "what-if" scenario, gave an indication of how communication and negotiation between these various parties would take place in real crisis situations. The scenarios described crisis situations (e.g., heat wave, power outage, crowd panic, resident fire) that were recognizable by all participants, but they also explored areas beyond the protocols and known practices of the professionals. In other words, the situations could not be resolved without cooperation between citizens and traditional parties. Both groups were given an illustrative picture of the scenarios and the associated data, see [illustration 1](#).

The following guiding questions were offered: What do you expect to happen in the first half hour? What will the different characters do? How will contact be made between volunteers and the traditional crisis response parties? Where will you get your information from? How will the situation evolve? One of the scenarios discussed was a crowd unrest due to gunshots occurring in Java Street - the main street in the Indische Buurt - during a King's Day celebration. Panicking people start running, pushing, and pulling, and the police appear on the scene to restore order. At the end of the street is a tunnel, where people are pressed together. Many people have to be taken to the hospital with shock symptoms and injuries. After 24 h of cooperation between a neighborhood community, spontaneous volunteers, and the traditional crisis response parties, the unrest dissolves and the situation goes "back to normal".

See [Illustration 1](#) in the Appendix.

Illustration 1: Scenario Java Street crowd.

Although the scenario was seen as quite extreme at first, the conversations also showed that such a situation could indeed happen. During the sessions, it became clear that the traditional parties were much better trained in working with crisis scenarios, which meant they could understand the nuances of the scenario more quickly. For citizen participants, the crisis scenarios evoked feelings of unease and insecurity. Some citizen participants (especially the elderly) needed more time to overcome that feeling. This was ulti-

⁶ <https://meevaart.nl/>.

mately achieved by linking the situation to comparable unsafe situations that they had experienced before, either personally or from the news. For example, one citizen explained what he went through years ago during a vacation:

Just imagine. A camping site where suddenly an insane storm came over at a quarter to six in a place near Bordeaux. Very heavy pine trees fell over there, over caravans. People were injured and two people were killed. A group of men started to help each other. They noticed what had to be done: those trees had to be removed from those caravans since there were still people trapped in the rubble. I don't know how that happened, but it happened. And I still cannot explain why some started to help and others didn't. There was just a group of men, I think there were eight of us or something, who started to help and that is what happened. That can also happen here.

During the discussions, see [picture 2](#), it became clear that indeed many citizens and local shop owners in the neighborhood would spontaneously offer their help. They would immediately start looking for information about the situation and for professional assistance. Adequate crisis communication was seen as extremely important. Any loss of communication from formal authorities would cause huge unrest on the streets. At the same time, people would look for places where information could probably still be obtained, such as in neighborhood community centers. Local shops and supermarkets would play an important role in hosting people running from the scene. The role of the community police officer was also considered very important (versus police officers coming from outside the neighborhood), since such officers have a lot of (general) information about the neighborhood and a large local network. Police officers with close ties to the community would play a major role in the dissemination of information during the crisis.

See [Picture 2](#) in the Appendix.

[Picture 2](#): Scenario session in the Indische Buurt.

6. The online COVID-19 living lab

The COVID-19 virus outbreak provided an opportunity to discuss a local initiative by a neighborhood community in the first months of 2020.⁷ In March of that year, “Samen Vooruit”,⁸ a local initiative in the Indische Buurt, set up a crowdfunding action to provide free meals to the most vulnerable in their neighborhood. According to its website, “Samen Vooruit is a network and collaboration of various (informal) organizations from Amsterdam East for further strengthening the neighborhood and the strength of residents, through co-creation with residents, professionals and the municipality on joint neighborhood themes”. The initiative's main concern at that time was for how people who could not easily rely on their personal networks (i.e., people with low social capital) could survive during the lockdown. Various spontaneous volunteers from local charity and citizens' networks and foundations were involved in preparing and distributing the free meals. The meals were prepared by chefs from local restaurants and by volunteers from “neighborhood kitchens”. The distribution, coordination, organization, communication, and crowdfunding campaign was all done by local volunteers.

In collaboration with members of Samen Vooruit, we set up digital sessions of what we called the Amsterdam COVID-19 Living Lab (as part of the Amsterdam Crisis Resilience Living Lab) in May and July 2020, during which community members, local entrepreneurs, and municipal officials addressed governance and coordination dilemmas related to the needs of the most vulnerable in the neighborhood. The central questions raised during this living lab were how the Samen Vooruit initiative is or should be related to existing, established institutions (such as the local food bank) and how the formal, municipal authorities could establish links with and between the various initiatives under the Samen Vooruit umbrella. In short, the Amsterdam COVID-19 Living Lab meetings focused on a concrete local concern but one that was recognized in other neighborhoods across the city and beyond, see [picture 3](#).

See [Picture 3](#) in the Appendix.

[Picture 3](#). Online scenario session about the COVID-19 response.

The Amsterdam COVID-19 Living Lab revealed not only the local patterns of inclusion and exclusion in relation to social work but also the unique characteristics of the networks and organizations involved in the crisis response:

- The actions of the formal, established health and social work organizations were based on rules and procedures but with a willingness to cooperate with the local, informal networks. It was difficult for the formal organizations to adapt to the new situation.
- The actions of the local, informal networks were based on ad hoc organizing through volunteers' action-oriented practices.
- The actions of the (local) government were based on legitimacy and accountability (who may do what, for whom, and when). This group hesitated to take on a coordinating role.

In May 2020, the first online session was organized in collaboration with Samen Vooruit. Participants – residents, volunteer social workers from the Indische Buurt, healthcare professionals, and civil servants from Amsterdam – mapped out what impact the COVID-19 crisis was having on the neighborhood and how residents and companies were responding. Participants concluded that the local, emergent networks in particular had been able to reach the most vulnerable, isolated people in the neighborhood. And because of the networks' local ties, they were able to respond to needs that were hidden from the traditional crisis response partners.

The session discussions made it clear that, during the crisis, the needs of vulnerable residents was one of the biggest concerns at the local level. Samen Vooruit worked closely with local stakeholders to respond to this urgent need, taking collective ownership of the response. However, the local initiatives struggled to tie their actions to those of the formal authorities. They therefore wanted the

⁷ See also Deliverable 1.1. of the EU H2020-SC1-PHE-CORONA-VIRUS-2020 101003606 Grant “HERoS: Health Emergency Response in Interconnected Systems.”

⁸ <https://samenvooruit.amsterdam/>.

municipality to play a larger role – not just financially (it provided a subsidy of €5000 for meals) but also organizationally. They felt the municipality's role should lie in coordinating the provisioning and distribution of meals to make these and similar initiatives more sustainable.

In addition, a discussion emerged on the definition of “vulnerable people” who relied on the meals. This was connected to the following questions: Did the people in need of help only become visible during the crisis, and if so, why were they so directly affected by the crisis? Why have they been under the radar for so long? Are these vulnerable people in need of other support as well? In other words, who exactly are the needy and is it possible to find them? Many different organizations are active in Amsterdam East, all working on complex social welfare issues in the neighborhood. They often have to deal with multidimensional problems that cannot be solved by one organization or institution alone. The participants therefore concluded that there was an urgent need for a coordination unit that could keep an overview of initiatives' and organizations' various activities and facilitate collaborations between formal and informal parties. Participants from the Municipality of Amsterdam suggested taking up these points for further action at the local district level and dedicating that task to a municipal department at a later stage.

An overarching theme for discussion during the Amsterdam COVID-19 Living Lab sessions was that the spontaneous initiatives and collaborations had been established in a very short period of time. Both formal and informal authorities expressed concerns about how to make these initiatives more sustainable so they do not simply disappear when the crisis is over. Trust building was seen as an important building block in creating sustainability for the spontaneous neighborhood initiatives that emerged in response to the COVID-19 crisis.

7. The evaluation and monitoring phase: results from the Amsterdam Crisis Resilience Living Lab

Over the past two and a half years, various parties have collaborated in the Amsterdam Living Lab. Its meetings provided insight into local dynamics during crisis situations. The evaluation and monitoring phase addressed the challenge of how the various parties involved in a crisis response can best join forces.

In the Zuidas neighborhood, the Amsterdam Living Lab sessions made it clear that the firms based there would indeed *extend* their actions in response to a crisis. Most would do so based on their current procedures and protocols concerning “business continuity”. This may also include collaborating with the formal authorities in certain cases, for example, if evacuation of office buildings is required. However, they are less focused on the neighborhood dynamics that arise during a crisis. In this context, cooperation between different parties – traditional and non-traditional crisis response organizations, private initiatives, and citizens – can function smoothly by using contacts that have arisen on the basis of mutual trust. Increased insight into each other's planned actions during a crisis is needed to estimate how each organization will respond to a given situation.

In the Indische Buurt neighborhood, the Amsterdam Living Lab sessions revealed that many *emergent* stakeholders will become active during crises. They are mobilized through resilient local networks, and their actions are seen as adding value to those of the traditional crisis response organizations. However, the various parties (formal and informal) are often not aware of each other's working methods, and the cooperation between them should be improved. Non-traditional crisis response partners in the Indische Buurt do not always feel understood or desired during crisis situations, even though they are willing to help where necessary. And traditional crisis response parties, such as the police and fire brigade, still find it difficult to involve non-traditional crisis response parties in the crisis response approach.

The Amsterdam Crisis Resilience Living Lab sessions provided valuable insights into crisis governance and citizen participation during crises. We offer three recommendations based on the lessons learned:

7.1. Recognize local networks and role shifts

This research has shown that the relationships between traditional and non-traditional stakeholders in crisis management are shifting. Our results confirm that partnerships between the local networks – citizens, private initiatives, organizations, and companies – and the (local) government contribute to an improved crisis response and management. In particular, the sessions have shown that local networks that mobilize during crises are of great added value because of their knowledge about and connection with citizens living in the neighborhood, including the most vulnerable. The local expertise provides opportunities for crisis management: from evacuation and first aid to transporting and caring for victims and from communication about the crisis to providing and sharing information. Local networks are also of great added value in relation to non-immediate acute help, for example, providing care for lonely and vulnerable people during a long-term crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

7.2. Invest in local networks and harness resilience

Connections between traditional crisis response parties and regional networks are increasingly important in crisis management. In both the Zuidas and the Indische Buurt neighborhoods, local networks were important for answering questions about the neighborhood: Who lives in the neighborhood and who is vulnerable? What are the characteristics of the activity in the neighborhood? What are the characteristics of the built environment? Who are the relevant local contacts? Where can information be obtained? However, in both neighborhoods, the traditional and non-traditional organizations are not always aware of each other's activities. The Municipality of Amsterdam and the Safety Region Amsterdam-Amstelland have the opportunity to bring these parties together in a coordinating role and to investigate how the resilience of these actors can contribute during crisis situations.

7.3. Promote the sustainability of connections

Crisis situations make existing invisible or latent patterns of interaction visible in the neighborhood. During the sessions, it became clear that old connections can be used and new ones established. What also emerged is that such connections can easily disappear once the crisis is over. Investing in sustainability is therefore important for the optimal collaboration between the parties involved. In doing so, it is important to recognize the significance of existing local networks in creating “embedded” initiatives during crises. By investing in sustainable cooperation at a local level, trust between the parties involved will grow. The involvement of both the formal, local authorities and the citizens' initiatives and networks is crucial in this regard.

While the living lab approach provided the opportunity to bring together otherwise isolated stakeholders, it is by no means the final solution. Previous research into living labs led to the conclusion that they indeed can create a sense of co-ownership and creative solutions for concrete problems. At the same time, the outcomes of living labs can also lead to temporal, local solutions, which are hard to maintain or to transfer to other places [54,57]. While this is a serious limitation of the living lab approach, we noticed that the crisis living labs in fact functioned as ‘catalyzers’: the local stakeholders in the Amsterdam neighborhoods remain in contact with each other also after the living lab meetings were over.

8. Conclusion

This article provides evidence of how collaboration between authorities (the municipality) and formal response organizations (such as the fire brigade and the police) at the one hand and local stakeholders (community organizations, citizens networks, spontaneous volunteers, firms and businesses) can make a contribution to the realization of a more resilient crisis management approach. However, the research also made clear that the lack of trusting relations and the lack of understanding of each other's perspectives may lead to missed opportunities or even frustration. The living lab approach that has been adopted in the research underlying this article proved to be a promising intervention instrument in this regard as it has great potential to bring together a diversity of partners to discuss possibilities for collaboration during crisis situations. Strengthening the links between traditional and non-traditional crisis responders can ultimately lead to a more inclusive and resilient crisis management approach.

The Amsterdam Living Lab sessions also taught us valuable lessons about the two Amsterdam neighborhoods. During the sessions, we noticed that local networks provided great added value because their members have in-depth knowledge about the neighborhood. It also became clear that the formal and informal actors were often not aware of each other's working methods. The established response organizations too often work in silos and are unaware of each other's protocols, procedures, and working methods and of the behavior of non-traditional response organizations be they expanding or emergent. This is in part because local initiatives are often organized in an ad hoc manner, whereas government organizations work with strict protocols and standard operational procedures. In addition, the knowledge and insight about each other's actions during a crisis situation is not always sufficiently available or communicated.

Perhaps the most important result of the Amsterdam Crisis Resilience Living Lab is the network that was created during its sessions. Participants from different backgrounds – official crisis response parties, city district organizations, social organizations, volunteer organizations, residents' associations, companies, and various other organizations – met and connected with each other through the Amsterdam Living Lab. They each contributed in their own way to the creation of insights and solutions and to trust building between the traditional, established response organizations and the non-traditional, expanding and emergent local actors. While gaining insight into each other's interests and working methods is crucial in adequate crisis response, further investing in cooperation between (official) governmental agencies and local networks can potentially reduce the tension between the parties involved and increase local resilience.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

Picture 1. Scenario sessions in Amsterdam Zuidas

Illustration 1. Java Street crowd

Picture 2. Scenario session held in the Indische Buurt

Picture 3. Online scenario session about the COVID-19 response

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